

**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЗАТРАТАМИ НА ЛОГИСТИКУ В
АВТОТРАНСПОРТНЫХ КОМПАНИЯХ**

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**RESEARCH ON THE APPLICATION OF LOGISTICS COST MANAGEMENT IN AUTOMOBILE
TRANSPORTATION COMPANIES**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье сначала излагается базовый теоретический обзор управления логистическими затратами и вводятся две концепции логистических затрат в узком и широком смысле. Общая логистическая стоимость относится ко всем логистическим затратам, понесенным от закупки сырья до доставки готовой продукции потребителям. Среди них транспортные расходы составляют самую большую долю общих логистических затрат, составляя около 45% от общих логистических затрат. Во-вторых, существуют складские расходы и расходы на обработку информации. Основными методами расчета логистических затрат являются традиционный метод расчета затрат и метод эксплуатационных затрат. Управление логистическими затратами является важной темой для современных компаний по производству автомобилей. Начиная с микроперспективы предприятия, в этой статье анализируется текущее состояние и проблемы управления логистическими затратами автомобильных транспортных компаний посредством анализа текущего состояния исследований управления логистическими затратами в стране и за рубежом; в сочетании с примерами анализируется контроль логистических затрат автомобильных транспортных компаний и предлагаются контрмеры для автомобильных транспортных компаний по внедрению управления логистическими затратами.

ABSTRACT

This paper first expounds on the basic theoretical overview of logistics cost management, and introduces the two concepts of logistics cost in a narrow sense and a broad sense. The total logistics cost refers to all logistics costs incurred from the purchase of raw materials to the delivery of finished products to consumers. Among them, transportation costs account for the highest proportion of total logistics costs, accounting for about 45% of total logistics costs. Secondly, there are warehousing costs and information processing costs. The main methods for calculating logistics costs are traditional cost calculation method and operation cost method. Logistics cost management is an important topic for current automobile manufacturing companies. Starting from the micro perspective of the enterprise, this paper analyzes the current status and problems of logistics cost management of automobile transportation companies through the analysis of the current research status of logistics cost management at home and abroad; combined with examples, it analyzes the logistics cost control of automobile transportation companies and proposes countermeasures for automobile transportation companies to implement logistics cost management.

Ключевые слова: управление затратами на логистику, логистические перевозки, автотранспортная компания, прикладные исследования.

Keywords: logistics cost management, logistics transportation, automobile transportation company, applied research.

INTRODUCTION

The most important thing to implement in transportation management is timeliness, accuracy and economy. The basic mechanism of enterprise activities is "input-conversion-output". For productive enterprises, especially steel enterprises, the input of raw materials, fuel, manpower and other resources are converted into products through manufacturing or processing. In the entire conversion process, transportation always runs through the whole process, and production logistics is the core, especially the transportation link, which must ensure the efficiency of the transfer of raw

materials, semi-finished products and finished products, reduce costs as much as possible, and ensure the smooth progress of production and even achieve time accuracy. Good transportation management can ensure that the goods are transported from the loading point to the unloading point in a timely manner according to the production, supply, transportation and sales situation, and shorten the time of goods in transit as much as possible, saving a lot of manpower and material resources for the enterprise, reducing transportation costs, improving the quality of enterprise transportation, and promoting the development of transportation management. "Through effective control of transportation

costs, scientific and reasonable organization of transportation activities, and strengthening effective control of expenditures during transportation activities, enterprises can reduce the consumption of materialized labor and living labor in transportation activities, thereby reducing the total logistics cost and improving economic and social benefits. Since the transportation management work of enterprises is relatively backward at present, it is particularly important for automobile transportation companies to do a good job in transportation management at this stage [1].

1. Logistics Cost Theory

1.1 Logistics Total Cost

The total logistics cost is an important indicator for enterprises to manage logistics operations. How to reduce the total logistics cost under the premise of maximizing corporate profits and meeting a certain level of customer service is a business goal of all enterprises. It should be noted that optimizing some logistics costs will reduce the cost of a single item of logistics, but at the same time it will increase the total logistics cost. Therefore, enterprises must regard logistics as an overall system and manage logistics operations with the goal of reducing the total logistics cost.

Total Logistics Costs = Transportation Cost + Inventory Carrying Cost + Logistics Administration Cost [2].

Obviously, this is classified according to the basic functional activities of logistics management. However, due to the cross-border (determined by the general requirements of collaborative operation) and openness (determined by customer service requirements) characteristics of logistics management operations, the total

logistics costs generated by a series of interrelated logistics activities are distributed not only in different functional departments within the enterprise, but also in different partners outside the enterprise. From the perspective of the value realization process of enterprise products, logistics costs are related to the production and marketing management of the enterprise - realizing the place (place) and time (time) utility of the product [3], and are directly related to the logistics service requirements of customers - as an interface for interaction with customers, customers must be satisfied. Therefore, even with such a seemingly simple and clear conceptual formula, it is actually very difficult for enterprises to accurately grasp the total logistics costs.

In reality, the concept of total logistics cost management is relatively weak in Chinese enterprises. They often only care about direct storage and transportation costs, but do not consider other parts of inventory holding costs and logistics administrative costs [4]. This is not only due to the lack of popularization of modern logistics management knowledge, but also the difficulty of grasping the total logistics cost in actual operation.

The basic content of logistics cost management: On the basis of logistics cost accounting, use professional economic management methods such as forecasting, planning, accounting, analysis and assessment to control logistics costs, including logistics cost planning, logistics cost accounting analysis, logistics cost control and logistics cost-effectiveness evaluation. See Table 1 for details.

Table 1

Basic content of logistics cost management

1	Logistics cost accounting layer	Clarify the composition of logistics costs; allocate and aggregate the total logistics costs according to certain standards, and make full use of relevant methods in management accounting to aggregate and allocate logistics costs; clarify the purpose of logistics cost accounting, and seek to reduce the total logistics costs by controlling and saving various expense items.
2	Logistics cost management	It means to manage and control logistics costs by using various cost management and management accounting methods on the basis of logistics cost accounting.
3	Logistics cost-effectiveness evaluation layer	On the basis of logistics cost accounting, the contribution of the logistics system to the enterprise's profits is evaluated, and the economic benefits of the logistics system are assessed.

1.2 Calculation method of logistics cost

Traditional cost calculation method: It is the traditional indirect cost allocation method. The specific methods include batch method, step method and variety method. In manufacturing enterprises, product costs are generally composed of three parts: direct materials, direct labor and manufacturing costs. Direct materials and direct labor are called direct costs, while all production costs other than direct costs are called manufacturing costs, such as depreciation, water and electricity costs, material consumption costs, indirect labor, etc. [5]. The cost of a unit product (service) is the sum of the direct costs and manufacturing costs after allocation. The traditional cost calculation method uses unit-level operation factors to allocate the manufacturing

costs of products. In fact, it assumes that the manufacturing costs consumed by the product are highly correlated with the product output. This method is feasible when there are fewer indirect cost items, the proportion of indirect costs in the total cost is small, and the cost management requirements are not high. Therefore, this method is more applicable to enterprises that produce a single product (service) or enterprises where the proportion of manufacturing costs is small.

Activity-Based Costing (ABC) is a cost calculation method that allocates indirect costs and auxiliary resources to each production activity according to a certain motivation ratio. It takes a specific item as the object, conducts quantitative analysis, and arranges the components of the object in order of their proportion to

the whole. It also divides the components into three categories, A, B, and C, according to a certain proportion or cumulative proportion standard. Category A is the focus of management, category B is the secondary focus, and category C is general [6]. The principle of the ABC method is to classify and manage according to the primary and secondary relationship indicated by the Barreto curve. This calculation method is widely used in the fields of industry, commerce, materials, population and sociology, as well as in many aspects such as materials management, quality management, value analysis, cost management, capital management, and production management. Its characteristics are that it can not only focus on key issues for management, but also take into account general issues, so as to achieve the best economic benefits with the least manpower, material resources and financial resources.

2. Analysis of the Logistics Cost Composition of Automobile Transportation Companies

The logistics system is a large system for every manufacturing enterprise. It is very important to formulate technical standards for facilities, machinery and equipment, special tools, etc. within the enterprise. Automobile transportation companies have long formulated a series of work standards for packaging, loading and unloading, transportation, etc. in various workshops and departments within the company, and set up a technical standardization room in the technical management department to study the coordination of technical standards and work standards in various subsystems and fields, and unify the standards of the entire logistics system. Logistics standardization unifies the basic equipment in the transportation process of goods, improves the versatility of equipment in the entire logistics process, and at the same time promotes the mechanization and automation level of the transportation, storage, handling and other processes of goods to a certain extent, which is conducive to the operation efficiency of the logistics distribution system, thereby reducing logistics costs.

2.1 Classification of logistics costs of automobile transportation companies

a. Supply logistics costs refer to the costs incurred in the logistics process from the purchase of raw materials to the supply to the purchaser. They include order procurement costs (wages of procurement department staff, travel expenses, office expenses, etc.), transportation costs (outsourced transportation costs, transportation losses, fuel consumption, and transportation staff wages, etc.), acceptance and warehousing costs (acceptance costs, warehousing operation costs), and storage and custody costs (warehousing staff wages, depreciation of storage facilities, reasonable losses, warehouse office expenses, interest on reserve funds, etc.) [7].

b. Production logistics costs refer to the costs incurred in the logistics process from the receipt of raw materials to the completion and storage of finished products, including internal transportation costs, depreciation of logistics facilities during the production process, interest expenses on occupied production funds, etc.

c. Sales logistics costs refer to the costs incurred in the logistics process from the completion of finished products into storage to the confirmation of sales to customers and delivery to customers. It includes finished product storage costs (salaries of finished product warehouse staff, depreciation, reasonable losses, warehouse costs, etc.), transportation fees paid during the sales process, depreciation of transportation facilities, fuel consumption, transportation staff wages, etc.

d. Waste logistics costs refer to the costs incurred during logistics activities such as the treatment and recycling of waste generated during the production process of an enterprise.

In addition, the costs involved in the company's logistics system include: direct labor costs, transportation costs, packaging costs, handling costs, warehousing costs), financial costs, office expenses, travel expenses, low-value consumables, and equipment amortization. Functional calculation refers to calculating logistics costs based on packaging, distribution, storage, handling, information, logistics management, and other functions. This method can show which function is more cost-intensive. In addition, the standard logistics cost (unit number, weight, and container cost) can be calculated to conduct operational management and set rationalization targets. Since the main logistics activities within the automobile transportation company, such as warehousing and transportation, have always been regarded as ancillary businesses of sales and production activities, the financial accounting of logistics costs has never been listed separately, but scattered in administrative expenses, operating expenses, financial expenses, and product manufacturing costs, making it difficult to summarize and calculate logistics costs, and it is also difficult to manage and control logistics costs [8].

2.2 Calculation of logistics costs for automobile transportation companies

a. The wages and benefits of sales staff are generally included in operating expenses. Therefore, they can be classified under the sub-account of sales logistics costs under operating expenses [9].

b. The purchase costs of production factors, including transportation costs and insurance premiums, are generally included in material purchases. It is only necessary to set up a sub-account for supply logistics costs under material purchases. When calculating product costs, they are allocated to the sub-account for production logistics costs in production costs [10].

c. Internal warehouse storage fees, such as maintenance fees and handling fees, are generally classified as administrative expenses, and can be grouped under the sub-account of supply logistics costs.

d. The wages, travel expenses, office expenses, etc. of purchasing personnel are generally included in administrative expenses and should be collected in the supply logistics cost sub-account under the administrative expenses account.

e. The transportation fee in the production process is generally included in the manufacturing cost. You can set up a third-level account of production logistics cost under the manufacturing cost account to collect the

logistics cost in the production process. When calculating the product cost, it is allocated to the production logistics cost sub-account in the production cost.

f. Depreciation expenses of relevant equipment and warehouses are classified into the secondary accounts of supply logistics cost, production logistics cost, sales logistics cost and waste logistics cost of different departments according to their different attributes.

g. Logistics information fees are recorded in the corresponding logistics cost sub-accounts when amortizing according to their attribution.

2.3 Characteristics of logistics costs of automobile transportation companies

First, logistics costs are not included in the financial accounting system of automobile transportation companies. Companies are still accustomed to including logistics costs in product costs. If you want to fully know all the real logistics cost expenditures, you cannot calculate or even distinguish between the logistics costs in the production field and the circulation field. Therefore, it is difficult for companies to fully calculate logistics costs, and they cannot calculate them separately and truly.

Second, the multiplication effect of logistics cost reduction. Logistics cost is similar to the lever principle in physics. The reduction of logistics cost can increase sales exponentially through a certain fulcrum. And a slight increase can also reduce sales exponentially. At present, the company has clearly recognized this from a qualitative perspective and has tried to adopt various measures to reduce logistics costs, but it has not yet been able to make a quantitative analysis. What kind of relationship is the multiplier relationship between logistics cost and sales? Further in-depth research is needed.

Third, the benefit contradiction of logistics costs. The "contradiction" phenomenon can also be often called the "alternating gain and loss" phenomenon, that is, changing any element in the system will affect the changes of other elements. To make any element in the system gain, it will inevitably have a detrimental effect on other elements in the system. Modern logistics costs include not only the logistics costs outside the company, but also the logistics costs generated by inventory, distribution, etc. within the company. These costs are often scattered in manufacturing costs, management and sales costs, and are not easy to be identified. For example, a series of expenses related to the company's logistics center, such as personnel expenses, equipment depreciation, infrastructure investment in the circulation process, and maintenance of goods in inventory, actually occur within the company but are difficult to clearly divide and calculate separately. These hidden logistics costs should also be an important part of the company's logistics costs.

For automobile transportation companies, if they want to implement modern logistics management as soon as possible, they must fully and correctly identify all the logistics costs incurred internally and externally in order to grasp the company's overall logistics costs. Therefore, under the current accounting system, auto-

mobile transportation companies should reduce logistics costs based on the company's overall costs. However, when trying to reduce logistics costs, they should also be careful not to affect the efficiency and quality of products and services due to reducing logistics costs.

3. Analysis on the current situation of logistics cost management of automobile transportation companies

At present, automobile transportation companies are in the initial stage of understanding and development of logistics cost management, and they still focus on circulation logistics while not clearly understanding the various logistics costs in production and operation. The management methods and importance of logistics cost management are still vague and not taken seriously. With the continuous research and development of logistics cost management in China, the leadership of automobile transportation companies has gradually begun to realize the importance of logistics cost management, and realized that logistics cost management is an important means to reduce the company's own costs and enhance competitiveness, and gradually began to promote logistics cost management in the company. The main problems in logistics cost management of automobile transportation companies are:

1. Automobile transportation companies have not yet completed the standardization work on logistics cost management.

Although automobile transportation companies have begun to unify the technical standards of internally circulated facilities, machinery and equipment, and special tools, such as packaging, loading and unloading, and transportation standards, they have not yet fully mastered the standards of parts provided by manufacturers in the procurement of parts, and the transportation cost standards of parts cannot be fully standardized and calculated, which is not conducive to reducing logistics costs [11].

2. The use of modern information systems to reduce logistics costs is not ideal. To achieve an efficient supply relationship between automobile transportation companies and suppliers and to ensure the smooth implementation of the (JIT) production system, it is necessary to use the construction of modern information systems, especially the use of high-tech technologies such as the Internet to complete the coordination, control and management of the entire logistics process and realize all intermediate process services from the network front end to the end customer. The current informatization and standardization of automobile transportation companies are not high. The logistics process is essentially a "three-flow integration" process of "logistics, capital flow and information flow". Only by effectively combining the three can the purpose of reducing circulation costs and improving logistics work efficiency be truly achieved. The backward level of informatization will not only cause direct economic losses, but also cause incalculable losses in terms of manpower, time, efficiency, etc. At present, the automobile transportation company's order sends logistics operation requirements and other information, but it cannot fully use the modern logistics information system to operate the company's intended quantity and

price. Some suppliers can only rely on telephone, email, express delivery, etc. [12]. Therefore, the coordination and cooperation of production plans with suppliers cannot be completed quickly in a short period of time. The material management system is still in the process of computer software system development and testing.

3. The ability to reduce costs through efficient distribution is not strong. Automobile assembly lines are required to be as efficient as possible, and a correct purchasing system is also an objective requirement for the development of enterprise logistics. However, with the need to reduce the cost of distribution as much as possible, especially with the development of high-frequency and small-unit distribution requirements, enterprises are required to adopt efficient distribution. They must pay attention to vehicle allocation plan management, improve loading rates and vehicle operation management [13]. Automobile transportation companies have not yet fully established a multi-batch, small-batch logistics system, and have not noticed that barriers between institutions, such as barriers between peers, have become obstacles to reducing costs and have caused idle resources. At present, it is still impossible to truly achieve a "zero inventory" cycle.

4. Automobile transport companies are still unable to fully utilize third-party logistics. Compared with the self-built logistics system of enterprises, the logistics services provided by third-party logistics are safer, faster, with higher service levels and lower costs. Self-built logistics requires: a large fixed asset investment. If the enterprise cannot effectively coordinate and integrate the logistics resources it owns, it will face huge investment risks and inventory risks. Through professional distribution through third-party logistics, it can fully utilize the scale benefits and professional advantages of third-party logistics, improve distribution capabilities, speed up the flow of inventory, reduce safety stocks, reduce the investment risks of enterprises, and realize the organic combination of the core advantages of enterprises and the dynamics of external market resources [14]. In addition to the logistics of complete vehicles, automobile transport companies are still unable to fully utilize third-party logistics for other purposes such as the purchase of raw materials, production auxiliary materials, and welfare products. Although the company's transportation team has gradually reduced personnel and transferred vehicles, the work of fully utilizing third-party logistics has been delayed due to problems such as personnel placement and the transfer of institutional assets.

4. Suggestions on the management of logistics costs for automobile transportation companies

4.1 Control methods for automobile transportation companies to implement logistics cost management

1. Adopt the horizontal management method of logistics cost, that is, forecast and plan the logistics cost. Logistics cost forecast is carried out before the logistics plan is prepared. It is to analyze the logistics cost of the current year, and on the basis of fully exploring the potential for reducing logistics costs, seek relevant technical and economic measures to reduce logistics costs,

so as to ensure the advancement and reliability of the logistics cost plan.

2. Adopt the method of vertical management of logistics costs to optimize the management of the logistics process. The logistics process is an economic activity process that creates temporal and spatial value. In order to provide the best value efficiency, it is necessary to ensure the rationalization of each link of logistics and the rapidity and smoothness of the logistics process [15]. The logistics system is a large and complex system. To optimize it, it is necessary to use advanced management methods and management means to formulate the optimal transportation plan using linear programming and nonlinear programming to achieve the optimization of goods transportation. The most common problem encountered in the logistics process is transportation. Linear programming and nonlinear programming optimization of factors such as the number of product suppliers, production site, geographical location of sales customers, frequency of transportation, mode of transportation, and transportation route can greatly reduce the logistics cost of products.

Use system analysis technology to select the best distribution method and distribution route for parts and products and optimize logistics. The distribution route refers to the route that each delivery vehicle must take when delivering goods to each customer. Its rationality has a direct impact on the delivery speed, vehicle utilization efficiency and distribution costs. Determine the economic and reasonable inventory level at each stage and optimize warehousing. Warehousing at each stage is the central link of the logistics system. The purchased parts must go through several stages from procurement to online production, and the reasonable inventory level and replenishment cycle at each stage, etc. Among them, the most widely used method is the economic order quantity model, namely the EOQ model.

4.2 Automobile transportation companies should establish and improve the management system of logistics costs

Automobile transportation companies should establish and improve the management system to reduce logistics costs. First of all, they should ensure the effective implementation of logistics cost management from an organizational perspective. Secondly, they should have a special logistics cost management organization to realize the specialization of logistics management. They should establish a modern logistics cost concept for all employees, re-examine the logistics system and logistics operation mode of the enterprise, absorb advanced logistics cost management methods at home and abroad, and find entry points for improving logistics management and reducing logistics costs in combination with the actual situation of the enterprise.

The content of logistics includes the type, quantity, time, quality, price, etc. of delivery. This information comes from various departments such as sales, design, production, procurement, and quality assurance. If a company wants to carry out efficient procurement, it needs the cooperation of various internal departments and the rationalization of the relationship between them [16].

In addition, the company will streamline the relationship with suppliers, actively communicate and cooperate with suppliers on the basis of information on inventory, demand, etc., and adjust plans and deliveries in a timely manner according to actual production conditions. At the same time, suppliers can adjust their plans in real time according to the company's real-time inventory, plan and other information, and can adjust inventory in a timely manner to reduce excess inventory. Suppliers establish a strategic partnership relationship, and gradually screen suppliers for reliable suppliers who are willing to cooperate with the automobile transportation company for a long time, and establish a long-term, mutually beneficial and mutually beneficial cooperative relationship.

4.3 Improve the incentive mechanism and strengthen the cost awareness of company employees

An important task of cost management is to establish and improve a set of cost control incentive mechanisms while strengthening cost management. On the one hand, a long-term incentive mechanism can be introduced to achieve indirect incentives for cost control; on the other hand, a cost saving plan can be implemented to achieve more direct and effective cost control incentives, that is, to establish a team of cost reduction personnel in each department, workshop section, and team, and timely calculate the actual cost of each department. Cost reduction work is included in the performance appraisal of the main person in charge of each department, and is directly linked to the benefits of ordinary employees [17].

Improve the awareness of cost management among employees, strengthen cost concepts, implement the principle of combining technology with economy and giving equal importance to production and management, carry out publicity and education on cost awareness to all employees, cultivate cost awareness among all employees, and change the cost management of a few people into management by all employees. The superiors are highly concerned about the training and use of cost professionals and take measures to actively hold various types of cost training courses, cultivate excellent physical cost and other cost management talents, improve the professional knowledge of company employees in cost, and further reduce logistics costs from the technical and economic fields.

CONCLUSION

Through the author's research, a brief analysis of the current logistics cost management of automobile transportation companies was made, and some conclusions on the logistics cost management of automobile transportation companies were obtained:

1. The understanding and development of logistics cost management by automobile transportation companies is just in its infancy. They still focus on circulation logistics, but have not fully realized that the scope of logistics is not limited to the circulation field, but also includes the production field. If logistics is to truly become the "third profit source" of automobile transportation companies, it must be reduced through effective logistics cost management.

2. Automobile transportation companies can effectively control logistics costs from four aspects: material procurement, transportation, inventory, and vehicle logistics. They should also improve the informationization, standardization, and rationalization of corporate logistics and make full use of third-party logistics resources to reduce corporate logistics costs.

3. Logistics cost management requires the joint efforts of all employees of the company. Only when all employees have established a sense of logistics cost and realize the importance of logistics cost management, can the automobile transportation company further strengthen the standardization of logistics, the construction of logistics infrastructure, the training of logistics talents, etc., thus creating a fair, reasonable and efficient development environment for automobile transportation companies.

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